

Case Study on Quality Education: Educational System with Undesirable Result

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Abstract:

Education has considered a robust weapon that provides power to his learner that can transform the world dramatically. Pakistan is among those nations, which are experiencing numerous issues of education. Numerous flaws are hindering educational growth in the country. Here in this study, we are trying to identify the key issues and problems within the educational system. According to the data obtained through a floated questionnaire, we have proposed achievable solutions & strategies to various problems for the enhancement of quality education, which can be achieved through the implementation of quality management in all areas.

Key Words: *Quality, Education, Private Sector, Parental Views.*

Introduction

Education has considered a robust weapon that provides power to his learner that can transform the world dramatically (Jain & Prasad, 2018). Universities & professional learning institutions can develop and transform the economic picture of a nation by producing quality human capital. Today's youth will hold the world in their hand tomorrow by what they have learned and experienced in their educational life. However, the immense role of basic & secondary education in this regard cannot be ignored that provides the basis for such tremendous transformations.

Education is considered the predictor of a country's next success. According to (Drew, 2019) five countries of the world are considered best in educational system and policies; as one of the developed country funded highly on the educational budget from government's federal and provincial taxes. Rest of developed countries has kept the education mandatory for aged 5 to 16 years where a national curriculum is followed that resists discrimination. Moreover, secondary education is compulsory in one of the countries worldwide. Their universities are considered the best educational forums and are highly recognized for transmission of education in the mass area.

But Pakistan is among those nations which are experiencing numerous issues of education. Numerous flaws are hindering educational growth in a country that should be settled. Individuals here are deprived of quality education as its framework does not compete with international standards (Rashid & Mukhtar, 2012).

Quality depends upon more research, standardization, and specialization within and outside the box. Pakistan's educational ranking is not so appreciative in this regard it ranked 125th out of 130 countries worldwide in terms of human education and skill building (Forum, 2017). Other neighboring countries are performing tremendously in this regard due to their well-developed & planned course of work and vision for qualified & productive individuals.

Here in this study, we are trying to identify the key issues and problems within the educational system and the ways through which it can be minimized to a good extent. The primary issue is imbalance among private schooling. Private schools have made this system a source of money printing within the country. Private schools mafia has set a trend of expensive education, and a race has been started for higher fee structure which is worsening the situation. The impact of this system has created a difference in economic classes that says only richer can send their children at best schools while poor's are thrown out of this high-class categories. Instead, the dissimilar curriculum in institutions affects Student's knowledge that differs significantly based on different criteria of providing education among schools.

Moreover, in the absence of the HRM department (human resource management), the hiring process of teachers is not adequate in the schools that can provide suitable and qualified staff for teaching. The teachers in institutions are untrained as they are offered low pay scales that are another reason for low motivation, quality and lack of training and development in the educational system (Rehman & Hameed, 2011).

The students are more focused on ratification rather than learning; a variety of subjects are available, that reduces their learning, conceptual and observing skills. This is the reason they do not enjoy their learning period; instead, they feel overburdened that hinders a student's personalized skill and creativity. Thereafter reduced linkage of academia and industry is a major problem as after having higher education student is unable to deliver what an industry demand for because universities are not focusing on producing what a market is looking for.

Background

Education can be taken as one of the key elements of each individual's life. It enables the person to logically analyze the changes around the world and respond to them, accordingly. An educated individual does not only make a practical decision but also could take the correct steps in the meantime. It empowers individuals to utilize their capability to attain their target successfully efficiently. Moreover, it plays a core job of making an individual a competent person in a society.

Relevant facts

Education establishes the framework for social political, what's the more, financial improvement of any nation. But in Pakistan, due to the oppressed state of education, it bears this fact that it can't protect its own segment. The rate of literacy in 2017-2018 recorded as 58% which has been ranked 129th out of the 137 positions with having 49.9% educated people on the international Index in primary education as compared to other countries (Alvi, 2018). According to the report of Human improvement, it has been observed that the rate of primary completion is 47.18% in males and 33.8% in females. The educational arena alone holds 317,323 academies out of which 197,000 are private academies that serve 20 million learners but are unable to provide quality education. This graph shows the current statistics on educational status.

Issues within Educational Arena

Pakistan as a creating nation has confronted many issues with delivering up to the mark quality in education since its commencement. There are different factors in charge of this circumstance. This section covers the problems we have analyzed through circulated question papers and observations.

The results of question paper circulated are displayed below

- **Absence of consistency or uniformity**

The educational system does not depend on uniform standards in Pakistan. The distinctive curriculum of education is at the same time working in the nation, which has brought different schools of thoughts in students' attitudes coming from public institutions, Islamic madras and a couple of elite private institutions. This has quickened polarization in the general society (Sayan, Fida, & Hussain, 2012).

- **Absence of professional improvement of Teachers**

Training is a basic need for quality execution. According to the current statistics of 2017 there, only 0.8% teachers are untrained as compare to the 27% untrained teachers in 2005, which shows improvement but teachers are not well polished as per the requirements of the time. Because of the different training establishment in Pakistan is not much resourced with qualified administrators or funds. It has been running worst with an inappropriate training standards and courses that are obsolete and exceptionally conventional which does not upgrade the abilities, skills, inspiration, and quality of teachers (Illahi, 1986).

- **Lack of quality teachers**

According to Rehman & Khan (2011) teachers are the backbone of the educational system. The nature of quality in teachers & instructions in schools is regrettable. According to the research, it has been found that the teaching style of teachers in schools is of poor quality. New techniques for teaching exercise planning are ignored by institutions. Cramming of lessons is being encouraged. Students don't have a clue about the utilization of libraries. In this way, the habit of reading is diminishing. Moreover, students are assessed on the remembrance of info and facts rather than performance.

- **Arrangement or system of examination**

As per the view of (Ghazi, 2010) the examination arrangement of institutes isn't just obsolete, but also it lacks in quality to assess the genuine accomplishments and performance of students completely. Only the student's memories are tested in the examination which advances illicit practices like, cheating that nullifies the students' intellectual power during the education process like, basic reasoning, reflection, analytical aptitudes, etc.

- **Overburden study**

Today students are too much busy and encompass a lot of school work or coaching classes to go to. There left no time to play and other activities; students are overburdened that devastates their interest in studying. Daily assignments and different lessons are only building their habit of cramming instead of conceptual and research building. The school's bags are burdensome that causes severe health issues within the students like back and neck pain, muscle fatigue, shoulder strain which affects the spinal curve. They also become shortsighted. The syllabus is exceptionally tough that becomes more complicated for the student to cover within mean time (Khalid, 1998).

- **The linkage between academia and industry**

In Pakistan, the fewer links between academic institutions and industry are also the hurdle in providing quality education. Industries hardly show interest in generating a network with universities. It is the necessity of education that students learn those practical skills and abilities which is needed in an industry that is not

providing in the country. In comparison with other countries that have a strong belief in this linkage and their R&D institutes are empowered and have strong industry linkage (Gul & Ahmed, 2012).

Summary of key problems highlighted in research questions

Alternatives Developed For Improvement Of Education Standard:

We have observed a number of issues within the educational sector of the country. With the quality concern, many amendments have been made by the government for which alternatives have been developed. Some of them worked really tremendous while others remain deprived let's take a look.

- After the privatization and decentralization process, an educational action plan for the period of 2000 - 2005 developed. According to (Lynd, 2007) in 2003 international targets adopted in Pakistan with a set target of 86% overall literacy to be achieved by 2015. 2003 was considered the revolutionized period for private schools, as incentives were provided to the private sector. For example, the Import duty exemption, subsidized land and utilities, tax exemptions, etc.
- According to Memon (2007), another alternative of education in 2007 evolved to update the previous standard of general and religious textbooks. Later this paper became the foundation for the development of new educational arrangement of 2009 as the previous policy did not generate desirable outcomes. The key reform of this policy was to extend free primary education and then secondary education by 2015 and 2025 respectively along with the promotion of private sector institutions.
- Another initiative in 2014 taken by the government was the promotion of private schooling in rural areas of Sindh. For this purpose, a government body joined hands with private entrepreneurs to provide low cost but standardized education to poorer. This was a partnership program by public and private bodies that focused on providing subsidies to those who fulfill a specific criterion (Chishti et al. 2011).
- Moreover, the education ministry also launched a quality assessment system to improve educational quality at the elementary level (Chishti et al. 2011).
- On January 2019 government official took notice of increased fee and as an alternative to this problem; ordered, private schools to reduce their fees by 20% which charge more than Rs. 5000 per month and adjust fee taken for summer break Javed (2019). Chief justice strictly orders to comply with these notices otherwise a fine Rs. 20,000 to 40 lacs would be imposed according to the law.
- Moreover to control excessive fee problem recently in September 2018 large microfinance institute and other private partners have developed financial products for such schools who comply with government loan policies will receive those loan and grants (Najam, 2017).
- An alliance of Private schools association has been developed to present, discuss and solve the prevailing issues of private schools. Their objective is to see the exact implementation of educational policies within the system and engage government and private bodies to resolve issues. This alliance has extended a number of meeting and training sessions for students and teachers for improving standards.

- Another initiative taken by the government was to improve rampant malpractice in the assessment system. Its objective was to provide particular training to teachers to utilize new techniques of the test, conversion of textbooks' various contents into test items to evaluate the student's performance on different objectives of education. Where Rs500 million has been allocated for this initiative.
- The government also emphasized reducing the corruption from the examination system by putting an effort to initialize a testing service where higher education admissions will be based on test criterion.
- Moreover, in another guideline, a great emphasis kept on giving autonomy to each board of education plus R & D cell to be established in every board to improve the assessment system (Kazmi et al. 2016).
- Azeem & Ismat (2016) in their study mentioned four years B.ED and two years ADE degree program was introduced as a mandatory requirement to educate the higher secondary.
- In 2010, to enhance research initiative, university- industry relationship, and to promote entrepreneurship, government bodies ordered to add research office in the higher educational institute (Raza, 2011).
- The governmental laws have bounded private schools to give free of cost education to at least 10 percent of the total strength of their students. This law has been amended in the year 2001, 2013 and 2018 (Samar, 2018).

Reasons for failure:

1. Lack of policy provision understanding, communication gap plus the inconsistent commitment of top bureaucratic & political leadership for policy implementation (Zaki , 1989.).
2. Ineffective controlled governance and corruption in the educational system (Rehman & Khan , 2011).
3. Centralization in consultation for the development of plans & policies with only concerned stakeholders.
4. Lack of both technical & financial resources plus lack in quality of human resources
5. Foreign aid & loans' dependence on financing the plans for development.
6. Minimum allocation of educational fund which is 2% of GDP. That is insufficient for the attainment of quality in education.
7. Poor training establishments with inappropriate training standards for the professional improvement of teachers.
8. Ineffective HR system for teachers' recruiting & hiring process.
9. Absence of incentives and remuneration for teachers for the attraction of competent and intellectual persons.
10. The tremendous growth in poverty, unemployment, and population which is the main cause of education decline (Yousaf, 2013).
11. A multi-tier educational system based on class structure, urban-rural divide, curricula, textbooks in private and public schools and gender discrimination (Hashami, 2016).

Presently impossible to implement

Everything demands changes within the system for their sustainability. Without changes, nothing in this world can last more than a short span. Every new philosophy brought by the new government is designed according to the present circumstances so for every next period it does not remain appropriate. Similar is the case with an educational department. A number of alternatives have developed for the betterment but not necessarily are appropriate for this time.

Although free primary and then secondary education for all was a good alternative, but this can never become possible until the government has sufficient funds allocation to upgrade the entire educational department countrywide. Our economic sectors are deprived of negative GDP growth and a budget deficit that hinders proper budget allocation. The mindset of people has now changed; people are now aware of international educational standards. They prefer private schooling and policies for their children, nor are they dependent on

government's old and outdated policies. A number of policies that are presented previously does not define any path or action plan to follow; how the incumbent government can implement a vague or incomplete pattern of the plan. Every initiative/goal requires a loyal and determined team of specialist individual who can work for national interest, Pakistan, unfortunately, is a patient of corruption cancer where people are continuously absorbing its resources for their own selfish interest and growth.

Quality management is a concept that can change every aspect of every department unless this is not implemented within the system no alternative and its outcome can bring desirable outcomes.

Teaching was once was a respectable profession, but now some of the selfish crocodiles have defamed this profession and resultantly lowered its quality standard. Their salaries are kept still too low how they can be able to focus on quality teaching if they are not freed from their financing issues as with the new advent of technology those alternatives have become outdated.

Suggested Solutions

We have seen every time alternatives have been developed to improve educational reforms in Pakistan. Unfortunately many have rejected as they were not implemented strategically. But proposing solutions should not be stopped here; in fact, strategic experimenting is good for effective improvement. So in this study, we are presenting a simple solution to crucial problems.

The **partnership program for public and private** is one of the solutions to many problems of both sectors schools. As this help public school student to access quality education and private schools would also be benefitting through incentives. These partnerships reduce privatization in the country as implemented in many schools of rural Sindh but provided the results that could be achieved after the privatization process. Many educationally developed countries are adopting this global trend in order to improve quality education.

In private schools, the **role of management** is appealing in some aspects. School management needs to develop proper **recruiting, training and HR system** in order to appoint teachers on merit. As every educated personnel cannot be a good teacher, teachers must be trained on modern modes of teaching. Research initiatives took in 2010 must be extended in schooling as well. Teachers should be developed through scholarships for Ph.D. programs to develop students instead of aware them only about education. If teachers are appointed on quality standards, the quality education issues would be resolved. A well-known country has developed top trained teachers by working on those aspects.

Teacher's salaries should be raised to a good extent, as Public teachers receive more salaries than private although the efforts are more required in the private sector. If they are released from financial concerns, would be more devoted towards making of a developed nation. In other countries, teachers are offered bonuses and incentives at their evaluation of hard work which results in highly developed teachers of the world.

The high **Fee structure** is not appreciable to fill bank accounts; Schools need to focus on their goals of existence - to provide quality education, instead of making their institutions money printing press. It is justified to have slightly more charges for cherries they are offering in quality, but that should be charged justly. As it became too difficult for parents to continue private education with such high fee and they were compelled to come over streets for protest; ultimately, government officials had to intervene to resolve this issue.

Private schools need to support disadvantaged children of society by providing **free education to 10% of total strength**. This law was again amended in 2018 by the government. If each private school starts to take this initiative many street children can gain the opportunity to become an asset of the country instead of getting manipulated by social evils. Some of the top schools are offering programs for financial aid to those children whose parents earn below the required level.

The uniform syllabus should tend towards improving the quality of education among students. It's the right of all children to access quality education; because curriculum differences create inequality among youngsters. The government had developed a framework for the equal quality of education in the country. Other countries are providing a uniform curriculum that gives the chances to the student to discover and explore themselves.

Academia and industry linkage must make sure that universities teach according to the modern market standards as students develop creative ideas that could benefit both the industry and academia. The industries can explore the potential areas of advancement whereas institutes can make students competent to the business world. As in international regions, many industrialists communicate with universities and get the ideas for their new innovations.

The malpractices in education and examination can be reduced effectively if the academics have good supervision and control over the enforcement of rules & regulation, teacher's hiring on merit, quality teaching material, and regular auditing and inspection of the schooling system. Because having a strong hold on these aspects will not only facilitate the schools to detect frauds but also enable them to take on time actions to ensure excellence in education. There are few nations that strictly work on these aspects.

Recommendation and Strategies:

Corruption is likely to concern all areas of planning and management, i.e., information systems, the building of schools, recruitment, promotion (including systems of incentives) and appointment of teachers, the supply and distribution of equipment and textbooks, the allocation of specific allowances (fellowships, subventions to the private sector, etc.), examinations and diplomas, out-of-school activity and so forth.

Education is all about life and demise for Pakistan. The nations are advancing so quickly that without imperative development in education, not exclusively we will fall behind others yet might be blot out altogether. As we have observed that Education framework is not so appreciative and if it is not changed, Country's economy will decline as well as would be unable to stay at sustainable position till the structure and systems are updated. Therefore, some of the steps that might be considered are:

Schools can maintain low fee if they are offered different incentives; Import duty exemption, subsidized land and utilities or loans, grants and another type of financing through government and private bodies. School financing facility can be extended to more private banks as well, with low interest and relaxing policies. This initiative: low fee but high quality education is possible as one of the public school has set a standardized example of this claim.

Uniform curriculum might be established through collaboration with developed countries. All private and government bodies could collaboratively set a standard of education in line with the international standard excluding double standards. These standards must be evaluated and updated according to the need of time which would not only benefit the society but also remove the sectarianism and inequality in society.

The recruitment system of hiring teachers can be effective by establishing a council for teachers, where a panel of teachers provides a license to the qualified teachers for the teaching program. Private schools can send their HR specialist to developed countries for training and teacher's escalation so; they can learn the feature of teaching and implement it to train teachers locally. Furthermore, offer a scholarship for the Ph.D. program to teachers for professional development during their teaching profession.

Corruption from the current educational system could be effectively eliminated if the academia and govt. I have clear regulations and norms. Visible procedures, and a framework of explicit policy for each & every task involved including skills building training for management & staff and assessment criteria. And Punishment for offenders, prosecution of approving case plus regular monitoring, accounting, and auditing that must be out of

line means of mafia and unlawful gratification. These initiatives would not only ensure literacy excellence & human development in Pakistan but will also improve the political and economic condition of a country that ultimately enables the govt. to enhance their budget allocation from 2% of GDP for education.

Conclusion

As we have perceived a number of prevailed problems within our educational arena, but we also know that for every problem there are definitely available solutions for it as well. Here in this case study, we have proposed a number of solution to numerous problems. If those recommendations are followed with proper planning and implementation, we can assume that our educational system will improve with great quality and enthusiasm. In this regard, we recommend that government and private both sectors should make efforts collaboratively in the best interest of their common people and for standardization of education as well.

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Annexure

CASE STUDY ON QUALITY EDUCATION

NOTE: This questionnaire is related to “Quality of Education” for conducting research. We need your participation and in this regard all the information are kept confidential and use only for the research purpose.

Name (optional): _____

Gender: Male Female

Age: 25-30 years 31and above

Parent’s Education level: Graduate Post graduate

Fee Structure (amount): _____

1. Do you think the fee structure at school justifies quality of education?
a) Yes b) No c) Neutral
2. Does your child is overburdened with variety of subjects available to your child at school?
a) Yes b) No c) Neutral
3. On average, how many hours do your child spends studying at home?
a) 1 hour b) 2 – 3 hours c) 4- 5 hours
4. Do you want improvement in the teacher’s training & teaching styles that help your child’s learning?
a) Yes b) No c) Neutral
5. In spite of studying at school do they need extra tuition for study?
a) Yes b) No c) Neutral
6. Do you think high fee structure & extra tuition charges can only provide quality education?
a) Yes b) No c) Neutral
7. Does your child receive knowledge, skills and attitudes necessary for learning throughout his or her life that matches with high standard education?
a) Yes b) No c) Neutral

8. Does your child receive career counseling & academic counseling at their institutions?

a) Yes b) No c) Neutral

9. Only your child's learning institute is accountable for his/her successful career?

a) If, Yes _____

b) If, No _____

Recommendation

Thank You

TABLE 1

1		yes /(1hours)	NO / (2-3 hours)	neutral / (4-5 hours)
2	1	15%	15%	5%
3	2	18%	10%	7%
4	3	11%	22%	2%
5	4	24%	8%	3%
6	5	21%	13%	1%
7	6	10%	21%	4%
8	7	19%	10%	6%
9	8	10%	18%	7%
10	9	10%	25%	0%

TABLE 2

1	Satisfactory level	Educational Standard	Fee structure	Teaching Expertise	school Management	Student Efficiency
2	Yes	40%	15%	24%	20%	11%
3	No	23%	15%	8%	43%	22%
4	Neutral	7%	5%	3%	7%	2%
5						
6						
7						